

TABLE 3 - VALUES OF $\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$ AND $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ IN UREA-WATER AND THIOUREA-WATER AT 303 K

Solvent % (w/w)	$\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ kJ mol ⁻¹
Chromium sulphate in urea-water		
11.52	11.39	46.75
20.31	11.62	54.03
29.64	11.90	53.58
36.83	12.16	59.52
Chromium sulphate in thiourea-water		
3.0	11.38	26.18
6.0	11.42	24.38
9.0	11.46	24.78
12.0	11.48	28.43

solvent compositions in each system. This implies that $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ may be determined by B -coefficient and $(\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)$ term. The positive values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ in both the systems, suggest that flow rate is not favoured by urea or thiourea content. Moreover, the value of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\ddagger}$ has been found to be greater than that of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\ddagger}$ in both the systems at 303 K, again conforming our conclusions from molar volume and viscosity data that chromium sulphate acts as a structure-maker/promotor in the entire range of solvent composition of urea-water and thiourea-water.

References

1. M. R. J. DACK, K. J. BIRD and A. J. PARKER, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1975, 28, 955; K. MIYAJIMA, M. SAWADA and M. NAKAGAKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1983, 56, 1954; M. WOLDAN, *Z. Phys. Chem. (N.F.)*, 1986, 150, 201; M. L. PARMAR and A. KHANNA, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.*, 1986, 55, 4122; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, 25, 1044; J. S. SANDHU and G. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 602.
2. D. P. SHOEMAKER and C. W. GARLAND, "Experiments in Physical Chemistry", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1967, p. 131.
3. G. K. WARD and F. J. MILLERO, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1974, 3, 417.
4. M. L. PARMAR and A. KUNDRA, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1983, 28, 1655.
5. D. O. MASSON, *Phil. Mag.*, 1929, 8, 218.
6. F. J. MILLERO in "Thermodynamics and Transport Processes in Water and Aqueous-solutions, ed. R. A. HORNE, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1971, Chap. 15.
7. F. J. MILLERO and W. D. HANSEN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, 72, 1758; F. J. MILLERO, *Chem. Rev.*, 1971, 71, 147.
8. L. G. HEPLER, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1969, 47, 4613.
9. G. JONES and M. DOLE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 2950.
10. H. S. HARNED and B. B. OWEN, "The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", 3rd. ed., Reinhold, New York, 1958.
11. B. J. BARKER and J. A. CARUSO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1973, 77, 1884; S. P. JAUHAR, J. S. BANNAIT, P. S. GURAYA and S. P. NARULA *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 797; N. P. YAO and D. N. BENNION, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, 75, 1727; A. SACCO, G. PETRELLA and M. CASTAGNOLO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1976, 80, 749; P. K. MANDAL, D. K. CHATTERJEE, B. K. SEAL and A. S. BASU, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1978, 7, 57.

12. R. L. KAY, T. VITUCCIO, C. ZAWOYSKI and D. F. EVANS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, 70, 2336
13. T. S. SARMA and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *Rev. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 2, 217.
14. D. FEAKINS, J. D. FREEMENTAL and K. G. LAWRENCE, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1974, 795.
15. S. GLASSTONE, K. LAIDLER, H. EYING, "The Theory of Rate Process", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1941, p 477.

Auranamide—A Phenylalanine Derivative from *Grangea maderaspatana* Poir.

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IN pursuance of our interest in Indian Compositae, we have recently reinvestigated *G. maderaspatana* and reported several clerodane, *nor*-clerodane, *seco*-clerodane, *nor-seco*-clerodane derivatives alongwith phenylalanine, hardwickiic and strictic acid derivatives¹. The phenylalanine derivative has been identified as auranamide (1) by Banerji and Ray². Subsequently, Talapatra *et al.*³ obtained the same compound and designated it as anabellamide. Previous work on this plant led to the isolation of a number of clerodane derivatives, polyacetylenes, flavones^{4,5}, chondrillasterol and chondrillasterone⁶.

Experimental

The air dried aerial parts (2 kg) of *G. maderaspatana* (obtained from M/s United Chemicals and Allied Products, Calcutta) were extracted with Et₂O-petrol-MeOH (1 : 1 : 1) mixture for 24 h in cold and the extract was concentrated under reduced pressure giving a greenish mass which was defatted by dissolving in MeOH and leaving overnight at 0°. The concentrated extract was column chromatographed over silica gel (B.D.H. ; 60 - 120 mesh) and following four fractions were collected: fraction-1 (petrol), fraction-2 (petrol-Et₂O, 3 : 1), fraction-3 (petrol-Et₂O, 1 : 1) and fraction-4 (Et₂O), Fraction-1 furnished α -humulene (40 mg). Fraction-2 was a complex mixture and separated on PTLC (SiO₂, PF 254) using C₆H₆-CH₂Cl₂ (1 : 1) solvent mixture affording phytol (200 mg), 3-hydroxy-8-acetoxy-pentadeca-1,9,14-trien-4,6-diyne (10 mg), lupeol (40 mg) and a mixture of diterpene acids (400 mg) which on subsequent methylation with ethereal CH₂N₂ and hplc separation (MeOH-H₂O, 9 : 1) over RP 18 (analytical column) gave methyl-10-*epi*-nidoresedoate (30 mg; R_t 11.8 min), methyl strictiate (100 mg; R_t 12.7 min), a mixture of methyl esters of centipedic and nidoresedic acids (170 mg; R_t 15.0 min) and methyl hardwickiate

(100 mg; R_f 16.6 min). Fraction-3 on prep.-tlc (C_6H_6 - CH_2Cl_2 - Et_2O , 4.5 : 4.5 : 1) yielded 3,8-dihydroxypentadeca-1,9,14-trien-4,6-diyne (6 mg), *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid (14 mg) and a complex mixture of diterpene lactones. The latter was treated with CH_2N and separated by hplc ($MeOH-H_2O$, 9 : 1) giving 15-methoxy-16-oxo-15,16*H*-strictic acid methyl ester (20 mg; R_t 6.6 min), 15-methoxy-16-oxo-15,16*H*-hardwickiic acid methyl ester (30 mg; R_t 7.0 min), 15-methoxy-16-oxonidoresedic acid methyl ester (16 mg; R_t 7.2 min), methyl *nor*-strictiate (24 mg; R_t 7.9 min), methyl *nor*-hardwickiate (10 mg; R_t 9.4 min) and methyl-2 α -acetoxyhardwickiate (42 mg; R_t 12.4 min). Fraction-4 separated on tlc (C_6H_6 - CH_2Cl_2 - Et_2O , 1 : 1 : 1) yielded 5,3'-dihydroxy-3,6,7,4',5'-pentamethoxyflavone (130 mg; R_f 0.33), 16-oxo-15,16*H*-hardwickiic acid (12 mg; R_f 0.35), 15-methoxy-16-oxo-15,16*H*-strictic acid (20 mg; R_f 0.30), (-)auranamide (1, 14 mg; R_f 0.40) and 5-hydroxy-3,6,7,3',4',5'-hexamethoxyflavone (40 mg; R_f 0.42).

Ir spectra ($CHCl_3$) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer, 1H nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) on a Bruker WM400 (400 MHz) spectrometer and mass spectra on a Varian MAT 711 (70 eV) instrument.

Results and Discussion

Auranamide (1) was obtained as a colourless solid, m.p. 203–04°, $C_{18}H_{16}O_7N_2$, $[M^+]$ 506.2200 $[\alpha]_D^{25} -35^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$ 0.05).

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Its ir spectrum displayed strong carbonyl bands at 1740 (COOR), 140 (CONH) and 1600 cm^{-1} . The 1H nmr spectrum (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) was in agreement with the reported data². The mass fragmentation pattern was identical to that reported for auranamide². The identity of physical and spectroscopical properties established that our compound was auranamide (1). Since the rotation was negative and similar to that reported for auranamide the configuration at both chiral centres was *S* as established earlier by the synthesis of auranamide².

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References

1. P. SINGH, S. JAIN and J. JAKUPOVIC, *Phytochemistry*, 1988, 27, 1537.
2. A. BANERJI and R. RAY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, 20, 597.
3. S. K. TALAPATRA, M. K. PAL, A. K. MALLIK and B. TALAPATRA *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1983, 46, 140.
4. F. BOHLMANN and P. K. MAHANTA, *Phytochemistry*, 1979, 18, 1067.
5. R. C. PANDEY, A. K. SINGHAL, N. C. BARUA, R. P. SHARMA, J. N. BARUAH, K. WATANABE, P. KULANTHAIVEL and W. HERZ, *Phytochemistry*, 1984, 23, 391.
6. C. S. IYER RUKMANI and P. R. IYER, *Phytochemistry*, 1978, 17, 2036.

Fruit Constituents of *Physalis minima* var. *indica* and One-step Conversion of Physalin B to 6-Epiphysalin G Acetate

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IN continuation of our search for withasteroids from *Physalis* species¹⁻³, we now report the chemical constituents of the fruits of *Physalis minima* var. *indica*, an annual weed of this region which differs from *Physalis minima* mainly by its more glabrescent leaves and distinctly five-angular fruiting calyx⁴.

Column chromatography of the petroleum ether extract of the fruits of *P. minima* var. *indica* resulted in the isolation of two constituents. The first constituent crystallised from benzene as pale yellow needles, m.p. 173°, and analysed for the molecular formula, $C_{18}H_{16}O_7$ (M^+ , m/z 344). It was recognised to be a flavonol from its uv spectral characteristics (vide Experimental). Its 1H nmr spectrum showed the presence of two *meta*-coupled aromatic hydrogens (δ 6.35 and 6.45, 1H, d, J 2 Hz each), a 1,2,4-trisubstituted-phenyl nucleus (δ 6.95, 1H, d, J 9.1 Hz; 7.73, 1H, dd, J 9.1, 2.2 Hz; 7.64, 1H, d, J 2.2 Hz) and three methoxyl groups (δ 3.87, 6H, s; 3.99, 3H, s). The compound gave a crystalline diacetate, m.p. 172–74°, whose 1H nmr spectrum showed additionally two 3H singlets at δ 2.35 and 2.45 for two acetoxy groupings. The data suggested the isolated flavonol to be a trimethyl ether of quercetin. The locations of the methoxyl groups in the flavone nucleus were considered to be 3, 7 and 4' from its uv spectral behaviour (vide Experimental) in presence of diagnostic shift